

Determination of Small Amounts of Arsenic and Tellurium with Periodate

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Arsenic and tellurium, in their compounds, are reduced to elemental state, separated and oxidised with metaperiodate and determined by titrating the equivalent iodate formed after masking excess of metaperiodate with molybdate.

S MALL quantities of arsenic and tellurium, in their compounds, are usually determined by reducing the metal to elemental state which is then oxidised with a suitable oxidant. Kolthoff and Amdur¹ described a cerimetric method for the determination of precipitated arsenic. Sloviter² used bromate-bromide solution for the same purpose. Evan estimated precipitated arsenic³ and tellurium⁴ with iodine.

The procedure reported in this communication consists in reducing the respective metal, in its compounds, with Bougault's reagent ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_2 + \text{HCl}$) and oxidising the precipitated metal, after separation, with excess of metaperiodate in borax medium. The iodate formed in stoichiometric proportion is determined iodometrically in chloroacetic acid buffer whereas excess of metaperiodate is masked with molybdate⁵.

The procedure reported makes the method sensitive. Quantities as small as 3.75 mg and 5.36 mg of arsenic(III) and tellurium(IV) respectively, in their compounds, have been accurately determined by this method.

Interference of tin, antimony, iron, copper, barium and calcium has been studied by adding 50 mg of each and it has been found that they do not interfere. However, mercury and selenium interfere.

Experimental

Solutions: 0.005 *M* solution of arsenic(III) was prepared by dilution of stock 0.05 *M* arsenic(III) oxide solution⁶.

Approximately 0.005 *M* solution of arsenic(V) was prepared by dissolving sodium arsenate (BDH, Analar) in distilled water. Its strength was determined iodometrically after reduction to elemental state with hypophosphite³.

Approximately 0.004 *M* solution of tellurium(IV) was prepared by dissolving potassium tellurite (BDH) in distilled water and standardised by iodine after reducing with hypophosphite⁴.

Approximately 0.005 *M* solution of tellurium(VI) was prepared by dissolving sodium tellurate (BDH) in distilled water and standardised by iodine⁴.

Bougault's Reagent was prepared by dissolving 20 g of sodium hypophosphite in 20 ml of distilled water followed by the addition of 200 ml of hydrochloric acid.

Chloroacetic acid buffer of pH 2.9 and 2 *M* molybdate solution were prepared as described in an earlier communication⁷.

0.1 *N* sodium thiosulphate solution was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of sodium thiosulphate crystals, $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH, Analar), in boiled out distilled water. The solution was standardised with potassium iodate.

Procedure

An aliquot, containing 3.75-18.76 mg, of the respective metal to be determined was treated with 20 ml of Bougault's Reagent. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for about half an hour. The precipitated metal was filtered through gooch crucible (porcelain type, having a filter bed of asbestos), thoroughly washed with distilled water and along with the filter bed was transferred to an Erlenmeyer flask containing an excess of potassium metaperiodate (50-100 mg) and 10 ml of $\sim M/20$ borax solution. The contents of the flask were boiled till the precipitated metal was completely dissolved, and cooled to room temperature. 2 *M* ammonium molybdate solution (10-15 ml), followed by 10 ml of chloroacetic acid buffer (pH 2.9) and 1 g of potassium iodide, were added and the iodine liberated

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF ARSENIC(III), ARSENIC(V),
TELLURIUM(IV) AND TELLURIUM(VI)

Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	Taken (mg)	Found (mg)
<i>Arsenic (III)</i>		<i>Arsenic (V)</i>	
3.75	3.73	4.22	4.25
5.62	5.60	5.06	5.10
7.50	7.45	5.91	5.98
9.37	9.25	6.75	6.75
11.25	11.25	7.81	7.80
13.12	13.08	8.44	8.48
15.00	14.90	10.13	10.15
<i>Tellurium (IV)</i>		<i>Tellurium (VI)</i>	
5.36	5.39	6.38	6.38
8.04	7.97	7.98	8.01
10.72	10.70	9.57	9.53
13.40	13.36	11.17	11.20
16.08	16.09	12.76	12.76
18.76	18.71	15.95	15.91

was titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. A blank was also taken. The results are given in the table 1.

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